

1 **Current trends for the reduction of fruit spoilage caused by enzymatic browning**
2 **applying physical techniques. Avocado pulp as an example.**

3 **Names:**

4 Victoria Jiménez-Trigo¹, Álvaro Fernández-Ochoa¹, Maria de la Luz Cádiz-Gurrea¹, Francisco
5 Javier Leyva-Jiménez^{1,2*}, David Arráez-Román¹, Antonio Segura-Carretero¹

6 ¹*Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, University of Granada, Fuentenueva*
7 *s/n, E- 18071 Granada, Spain*

8 ²*REQUIMTE/LAQV, Polytechnic of Porto – School of Engineering, Rua Dr. António Bernardino*
9 *de Almeida, 4249-015 Porto, Portugal*

10 *Corresponding author:

11 Francisco Javier Leyva-Jiménez, ORCID: **0000-0002-9589-7388**

12 E-mail: javier.leyva@ugr.es

13 Telephone number: +34 926295300

14

15

16

17

18 **Abstract:**

19 The avocado fruit (*Persea americana*) and its related products are becoming
20 increasingly in demand worldwide because of their high nutritional value. Due to its
21 composition, avocado pulp has a very short shelf life, causing significant economic losses
22 and food waste, most of them related to enzymatic browning. Considering the increasing
23 interest in avocado and its derivative products, the present review collates the information
24 published in scientific literature associated to the physical methods employed in the
25 inhibition of avocado polyphenol oxidase (PPO). Physical methods can disrupt the PPO
26 activity, their main advantage lies in enhancing the shelf life of products without changing
27 their composition or recipe. Some of these technologies are pasteurisation, high
28 hydrostatic pressure (HHP) treatment, radiation, electromagnetic or mechanical waves
29 application. Future research should focus on the optimization of these technologies and
30 the evaluation of their combined effects.

31

32 **Keywords:** Enzymatic browning; Food preservation; Avocado; Polyphenol oxidase;
33 Phenolic compounds; Physical methods;

34 **Introduction**

35 In recent decades, the consumption of healthy, natural, and sustainable products,
36 such as fruits and vegetables, has increased worldwide. This trend may be linked to
37 changing attitudes among the population, who are becoming more aware of the
38 importance of adopting a healthy lifestyle to improve their quality of life (1). This
39 upward tendency may be related to the well-known beneficial effects of fruits and
40 vegetables against many diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, lung
41 diseases or immune disorders (2,3). However, people's hectic lifestyles make it
42 difficult to prepare meals due to lack of time, resulting in the consumption of high-
43 calorie foods with poor nutritional value. In recent years, the food industry has
44 developed new ready-to-eat products with improved nutritional profiles, and avocado
45 products are an example of ready-to-eat products that have recently attracted
46 increasing consumer interest. Currently, the avocado has become one of the most
47 important natural products in European Union being the volume of avocado production
48 of approximately 150 thousand tons in 2022, 72% of which was produced in Spain
49 (4,5).

50 One of the reasons for its growing importance is its ideal nutritional profile, which
51 is characterized by a high lipid content with a ratio of unsaturated to saturated fatty
52 acids of approximately 6:1, predominantly oleic acid, which accounts for 59% of the
53 avocado's lipid content. The rest of the lipid profile comprises 14% saturated acids,
54 mainly palmitic acid, and 11% polyunsaturated acids, mainly linoleic acid (6).
55 Although the interesting lipid content of this fruit is its main attraction, phenolic
56 compounds have also been identified in its composition, which are characterized by
57 their antioxidant capacity (7). Phenolic acids such as protocatechuic acid, gallic acid

58 and syringic acid or flavonoids such as catechin, quercetin or rutin have been reported
59 in high concentrations in the pulp of this fruit (Table 1).

60 Due to its composition, avocado fruit has a very short shelf life, causing significant
61 economic losses and food waste (13). An important part of these losses is related to
62 spoilage caused by enzymatic browning (14). This biochemical process can be defined
63 as the oxidation of phenols into coloured quinones resulting in a gradual change in the
64 colour of the green avocado pulp to brown (15). This oxidative process consists in a
65 first hydroxylation of monophenols to o-diphenols and a second hydroxylation of these
66 compounds to o-quinones, which can polymerize to brown pigments, also known as
67 melanins (16) (Figure 1). These reactions are mainly mediated by the enzyme
68 polyphenol oxidase (PPO), a copper-containing phenolase present in plants (17). This
69 enzyme can initiate browning when the integrity of the membrane is compromised by
70 physical damage, such as bruising, cutting, peeling, biotic stress, or post-harvest
71 senescence. This situation may trigger enzymatic browning through the release of
72 phenolic compounds bounded by the tonoplast in vacuoles, interacting with PPO
73 located in chloroplasts and cell walls. In this sense, the greater the membrane damage,
74 the higher the melanin production due to greater phenolic compounds release (16,18).

75 As is the case with other enzymes, the activity of PPO can be modified by different
76 exogenous factors. Among them, temperature and pH are reported to be the main
77 factors that modulate the activity of PPO (17). Depending on the source of the enzyme,
78 the optimal temperature and pH may differ (19). For fruits and vegetables, the optimal
79 temperature is found around 25-45 °C (20–22). On the other hand, almost all fruits and
80 vegetables have a similar optimal pH, which oscillates between 6-7.5. In the case of
81 avocado, the highest activity of avocado PPO is reached at 20°C and an optimal pH of
82 6.5 (23).

83 These data are essential to focus on the strategies to control food spoilage related
84 to PPO activity (24). On this scenario, the main strategies applied to control the effects
85 of PPO in food by inhibiting or reducing the activity of this enzyme may be focused
86 on: a) the change of environmental conditions (temperature and pH); b) the enzyme
87 disruption; c) reduction of availability of substrates; d) limitation of oxygen
88 availability and e) the reduction of external damage to the avocado fruit (16,25).

89 In this sense, traditionally chemical methods based on the use of antioxidants,
90 chelating agents or acidulants are the most applied strategies because of the ease of
91 incorporation into products and the cost-benefit ratio (15) (Figure 1). Thus,
92 antioxidants such as ascorbic acid or melatonin can reduce the colour changes due to
93 enzymatic browning in avocado by reducing the availability of PPO substrates (26,27).
94 In other hand, chelating agents can also form complexes with PPO or react with
95 substrates, resulting in partial or total inhibition of the enzyme (28). In this sense,
96 substances such as kojic acid (29) or oxalic acid (30) have shown strong chelating
97 properties as preservatives in the food industry. Finally, acidulants are compounds that
98 have the effect of lowering the pH of the medium, thereby reducing the activity of the
99 enzyme. Thus, acids such as citric or acetic acid, have also been used as acidulants
100 (15).

101 Despite the advantages of chemical methods of PPO inhibition, consumers are
102 rejecting the addition of additives to natural products to extend their shelf life. This
103 trend has encouraged the development of clean label products, which advocate the use
104 of clear labels without misleading ingredients/additives. Therefore, physical methods
105 are emerging as interesting alternatives to solve these issues, as the list of ingredients
106 remains unchanged. These methods aim to inactivate PPO by disrupting the enzyme,
107 causing denaturation or modification of the active site, limiting oxygen, or protecting

108 the integrity of the membrane, as shown in Figure 1. Thus, heat treatments or high
109 pressures applications, for example, achieve partial or total inhibition of the enzyme.
110 Another physical approach is to limit the oxygen available by modifying the packaging
111 atmosphere to reduce enzyme activity. Finally, the application of magnetic fields
112 improves the integrity of the membrane, preventing the release of the PPO substrate
113 and thus delaying browning. Although the use of these techniques in food industries
114 are limited due to their high cost or difficulty of application, the current demand from
115 consumers for natural products without the use of additives has made these techniques
116 may emerge as an interesting alternative for avocado fruit preservation in recent years.
117 The advantages and disadvantages of the different physical methods are presented in
118 the Table 2.

119 Considering the growing interest of the food industry in the preservation of
120 avocado fruit and according to our literature survey, so far, no review articles have
121 been published on the application of physical methods for the inhibition of PPO in
122 avocado pulp. Thus, the present review comprehensively discusses the effectiveness
123 of traditional and innovative physical methods for PPO inhibition in avocado pulp and
124 provides, for the first time, an overview of the applicability, advantages and
125 disadvantages and potential use of these methodologies to reduce enzymatic browning
126 in avocado pulp.

127 **Material and methods**

128 *Search strategy and selection criteria*

129 In light of the growing interest in avocado fruit and its related products in recent years
130 (Figure 2), it was deemed appropriate to direct the following research towards the

131 elucidation of alternative methods to inhibit enzymatic browning in avocado fruit and
132 consequently, the reduction of avocado pulp spoilage.

133 All the data collected in this work has been compiled from Scopus, PubMed and Web
134 of Science database applying in the search the following keywords: “avocado”
135 “guacamole” “physical methods” “heat” “pressure” “ultrasound” “radiation” “cold
136 plasma” “electromagnetic” “electric” “storage” “atmosphere” “gas” “microwave”
137 “polyphenol oxidase” “enzymatic browning”. Other related keywords were added to
138 expand the research strategy: “color stability”, “coloration”, “polyphenol oxidase” and
139 “total antioxidant activity”.

140 The search strategy based on the aforementioned methodology yielded 65 studies. Due
141 to the paucity of found studies, no age restrictions were considered. Therefore, the final
142 set of studies included in the analysis were those that had employed the use of avocado
143 pulp. Following an initial assessment of the title and abstract, studies deemed to be
144 irrelevant to the subject matter were rejected, for example the use of avocado fruit in the
145 development of natural pigments related with enzymatic browning. In addition, studies
146 that applied combined inhibition method, chemical and physical, and the main inhibition
147 effect was induced by chemical treatment were also excluded. Furthermore, studies that
148 did not achieve the primary inhibition effect due to a physical treatment method were also
149 excluded. Lastly, studies that yielded inconclusive results or that were deemed to be non-
150 comparable were excluded from the review.

151 **Physical methods for avocado PPO inhibition**

152 *Thermal processes*

153 Thermal processes are the most applied physical methods to increase the shelf-life of
154 products in the food industry. They are based on the application of temperature, or the

155 effect of heat generated by other processes to obtain a partial or total reduction of enzyme
156 activity by the denaturalization of the enzyme. Although heat treatment is the most
157 applied technique, its application presents some drawbacks in food attributes such as loss
158 of colour, texture, flavour and nutrient quality degradation (31). Conversely, cold
159 treatment or storage is a common method used to extend the shelf life of products for
160 weeks or even months. Unlike heat treatment, freezing preserves the taste, aroma, or
161 flavour of the product. Nevertheless, irreversible changes in the texture of the food may
162 occur if the correct cold chain or freezing process are improperly applied. However, it is
163 important to note that the reduction of enzymatic browning due to cold treatment or
164 storage is limited just before to the moment of defrosting or returning to room temperature
165 (32). For this reason, this methodology is not considered as a technological treatment for
166 PPO inhibition because the enzymatic browning could be initiated after defrosting and
167 could even increase the production of melanins due to cell membrane disruption induced
168 by a wrong freeze procedure. Therefore, heat treatments on avocado fruit are currently
169 the most commonly used.

170 *Blanching and pasteurization*

171 Blanching and pasteurization are the most commonly used heat treatments in the food
172 industry to reduce the enzymatic browning in their products. Blanching is a technique that
173 uses water or steam at high temperature (≥ 100 °C) and low times (2-10 min) (33). Thus,
174 studies conducted on plants have shown that blanching is effective in inhibiting PPO
175 activity even when applied for seconds (34). In other hand, pasteurization is a technique
176 that uses temperatures between 60-100°C for some minutes or medium-long periods of
177 time (around 15-30 minutes) (35,36). Although of heat treatment is the most effective
178 process applied to inhibit PPO through partial or total enzymatic inhibition, it induces
179 sensory and nutritional changes, such as loss of nutritional value, changes in texture, and

180 leads to bitter flavours, resulting in a reduction of product quality (31,37). However, the
181 reported study by Li *et al.* demonstrated that the application of lower air or water
182 temperatures (45°C) for long periods (> 30 min) reached to inhibit the activity of PPO
183 efficiently reducing the negative effects on the sensory quality of foods (38). These
184 promising results may be useful for the inhibition of PPO in avocado pulp without
185 seriously affecting its sensory properties.

186 When thermal treatment is applied to avocado, it is necessary to consider that avocado
187 PPO has been found to have higher activity and heat resistance compared to PPO in other
188 fruits. Thus, although the optimal activity temperature of avocado PPO is 20°C, its
189 activity continues within a range of 60-65°C, and further increases in temperature result
190 in higher inactivation (39,40). For this reason, the current studies focused on the
191 application of temperatures above the inactivation point of avocado PPO (<65°C) with
192 shorter times (\leq 5 minutes). For instance, some studies that applied temperatures above
193 70°C for 3-5 minutes demonstrated a significant increase in the stability of avocado puree,
194 maintaining the green colour and increasing the brightness of the product (41,42).
195 Moreover, this thermal treatment was compared with the addition of 2% (w/w) of citric
196 acid, revealing greater inhibition when heat was applied. In addition, other treatments
197 with lower temperatures (38°C) and longer times (30, 60 and 90 minutes) have also been
198 evaluated, resulting in a reduction of enzymatic browning impact and an increase in
199 avocado shelf life (43,44). However, the efficiency of heat treatment may also be
200 influenced by the pH of the medium in which it is applied. Weemaes *et al.* conducted a
201 study that demonstrated that the temperature required to reduce the activity of PPO is
202 directly proportional to the pH. Therefore, a lower pH of the medium requires a lower
203 temperature to inactivate PPO (45).

204 Similar synergistic effects were presented by the application of high temperatures and
205 high pressures. In this sense, Albahr et al. used pressure-assisted thermal sterilization
206 (PATS) with an initial vessel temperature of 90°C for 5 minutes to produce a stable
207 avocado puree that remained stable for 3 months (46). However, they did not conduct
208 sensory analyses to determine whether the high temperature treatment induced changes
209 in flavour, as observed in other studies (42). In the same line, Sarantakou et al. (2023)
210 conducted a study evaluating sensory analysis in avocado smoothies treated under lower
211 temperatures (25-30°C) at the same pressure conditions (\approx 700 MPa). The results showed
212 that the product was accepted by consumers as freshly prepared smoothies, with good
213 results in PPO inactivation assays (<10% residual PPO activity) and microbiological
214 analysis (47).

215 According to the compiled results, the application of temperatures (30-70°C) with shorter
216 times induces significant PPO inactivation. However, the texture or colour may be
217 affected after the treatments. With the purpose of solving these drawbacks, the
218 combination of heat treatments and high pressures may provide an interesting balance
219 between PPO inactivation and the sensory quality of avocados.

220 *Microwaves treatment*

221 Treatment with microwaves is widely used in food processing. Microwaves are
222 electromagnetic waves with frequencies between 300 MHz and 300 GHz and
223 wavelengths from 1 mm to 1 m. It produces rapid heating based on the ability of dielectric
224 materials, such as water, to absorb microwaves. Thus, the friction between dielectric
225 molecules present in the food structure generates thermic energy, resulting in a fast
226 heating (48–50). This rapid heating may help to preserve the antioxidant capacity and
227 total polyphenols and flavonoids content while inactivating PPO by protein

228 denaturalization, making it a promising treatment in the food industry (51). Although
229 some research has evidenced the non-thermal effects of microwaves on PPO inhibition
230 (48), most of them have noted that PPO inhibition is induced by the heat produced by
231 microwaves (52,53). On the other hand, the use of microwave technology also has some
232 disadvantages. First, microwave-compatible vessels are necessary for heating food
233 materials in commercial microwaves. It is important to note that the use of such vessels
234 may incur additional costs for the food industry. Moreover, commercial microwaves can
235 also produce non-homogeneous heating or burns due to overheating. Finally, if the
236 microwave heating procedure is not properly adjusted considering the type of food, the
237 sensorial quality of the product may be reduced (54).

238 According to studies available in the literature, microwaves have been found to be
239 effective in inhibiting avocado PPO. Thus, two studies conducted under the same
240 microwave conditions (11.0W/g for 80 s) showed that avocado PPO activity was reduced
241 by more than 80%. In a study conducted by Ospina *et al.*, an inhibition of over 95% was
242 achieved with avocado purée (52). Similarly, Zhou *et al.* obtained an 80% reduction in
243 defatted avocado purée, which maintained a constant residual PPO activity of 20% after
244 treatment with a modified domestic microwave. These results could be explained by the
245 difference in fat content between the formats of avocado fruit used in each study. Guzmán
246 *et al.* also achieved a constant colour of microwaved avocado purée for one week, without
247 affecting its taste or odour, treating the purée with 633W for 30 seconds (53). Although
248 no further studies have been conducted on the sensorial profile evaluation of avocado
249 fruit after microwave treatment, the results obtained in the previous study are in line with
250 other studies conducted on fruits such as raspberry or traditional food plants. These
251 studies confirmed that microwave treatment is a potential method for extending the shelf-
252 life of fruits and vegetables while maintaining their nutritional value at a low cost (55,56).

253 The efficacy of microwave treatment on avocado fruit can be confirmed by conducting
254 future studies. These studies could assess the impact of varying pH levels, treatment
255 times, and other conditions on avocado in different formats presented in the food industry.

256 *Ultrasounds treatment*

257 Ultrasounds is a non-thermal technology that uses mechanical waves with frequencies
258 in the range of 20-100 kHz exceeding the human hearing limit (57). The main interest of
259 this treatment is the acoustic cavitation (AC) phenomenon, which occurs when ultrasound
260 waves pass through a liquid medium and dissolved gas oscillates due to the influence of
261 the acoustic field (58). Thus, the process generates phases of expansion and compression,
262 leading to the formation, expansion, and collapse of cavitation bubbles. When these
263 bubbles violently collapse, they create high-temperature conditions that cause chemical
264 and cellular alterations. In the case of proteins, this results in structural modifications that
265 affect molecular interactions between the protein's components and other molecules (57).
266 These processes can affect the texture of products, such as juices, and impact the activity
267 of food enzymes (57,59).

268 The available results on the effect of ultrasound on PPO activity are controversial as
269 its usefulness remains unclear. A study comparing pasteurization and ultrasound
270 treatment found that frequencies of 40 kHz for 10 minutes were more effective than
271 pasteurization treatment in reducing PPO activity in avocado pulp, although treatment
272 with lower times or frequencies was less effective (60). In contrast, Bi et al. found that
273 ultrasounds increased PPO activity in diluted avocado pulp when using a frequency of 20
274 kHz for an interval of 0 to 10 minutes. However, the same study reported that ultrasound
275 treatment decreased the colour changes measured by colorimetry (61). Due to the lack of
276 studies verifying the effect of ultrasound in inhibiting avocado PPO, further investigations

277 are needed to fully understand the effects of this technology in controlling browning in
278 avocado products.

279 *Non-thermal processes*

280 Over the last decades, the food industry has been exploring non-thermal processes as
281 an alternative to traditional methods that rely on temperature sources. The goal of using
282 non-thermal technologies is to overcome the drawbacks associated with thermal
283 processes, such as the development of bitter flavours or textural changes of food products.
284 These technologies are based on the application of pressure, radiation, electromagnetic
285 fields, and gas treatment or atmosphere modification. The application of these innovative
286 technologies is an effective method for reducing the activity of enzymes associated with
287 enzymatic browning through conformational changes or enzyme denaturation while
288 maintaining the sensory profile (16). Therefore, these technologies have great potential
289 for application in the food industry and should be considered as interesting alternatives.

290 *High Hydrostatic Pressure treatment*

291 High Hydrostatic Pressure (HHP) is the most commonly used non-thermal method to
292 preserve food, which can affect the enzyme activity due to the effect of pressure without
293 reaching high temperatures. This technology is based on both Le Chatelier principle: a
294 system under pressure adopts molecular configurations and adjusts the rate of chemical
295 reaction to achieve the lowest volume; and Pascal principle: the applied pressure is
296 uniformly transmitted in all directions of the fluid and its surroundings (62,63). The HHP
297 treatment applies pressure equally throughout the product, promoting reactions when the
298 volume is reduced (63). Thus, the product placed in the HHP chamber must be
299 hermetically sealed in a flexible container that can resist the pressure transmitted to the
300 food by a liquid medium, generally water (64), which can absorb a part of the heat

301 generated by the increase in pressure. The procedure of HHP is graphically schematized
302 step by step in Figure 3.

303 The most important advantage of applying HHP is the maintenance of the nutritional
304 value of fruits and vegetables, especially thermolabile nutrients (65). In industrial units,
305 the pressure is limited to 600 MPa maximum (65), but overall, pressures between 100 and
306 800 MPa are applied for variable periods of time in HHP treatment to unfold the proteins,
307 changing their tertiary and quaternary structures by breaking the bounds that conform
308 them and consequently, losing their active properties (37,62,66). Therefore, the main
309 purpose of this method is to inactivate microorganisms, by destabilizing the cellular
310 membrane and enzymes present in foods to extend their shelf life without altering the
311 organoleptic profile of the product (64).

312 According to previously reported studies, the pH influenced on the high pressure
313 processing (HPP) effectiveness to inhibit avocado PPO. Thus, at lower pH conditions,
314 lesser pressures were required to inactivate PPO. For instance, in studies conducted in
315 acidic mediums ($\text{pH} < 4.6$), a pressure of approximately 600 MPa was necessary to cause
316 a 50% reduction in PPO residual activity (46,47), whereas pressures higher than 800 MPa
317 were needed in neutral or basic pH (45,67,68). Despite the advantages of HPP treatment
318 on food preservation, the main drawback is the possible reactivation of PPO during
319 storage, resulting in avocado quality deterioration (47).

320 Furthermore, the effectiveness of HHP treatment in avocado PPO activity is
321 influenced by other factors, including the temperature reached during treatment, storage
322 and the number of HHP cycles. Although current studies are needed, previous research
323 has demonstrated that higher temperature treatments, higher number of HHP cycles, and
324 lower storage temperatures are useful for PPO inhibition (67,69). However, other studies

325 have reported contradictory results. Thereby, Weemaes et al. demonstrated an
326 antagonistic effect of pressure and temperature: high pressures induced a higher
327 inactivation rate of PPO at low temperatures (70). Other research even found that HHP
328 treatment at 600 MPa in avocado slices at temperatures below 40 °C produced an increase
329 in PPO activity because it induced changes in wall structures and cellular networks and,
330 consequently, triggered the enzymatic browning (71). Given the scarcity of reports on the
331 effect of HPP on the inactivation of avocado PPO, further studies are needed to clarify
332 the effect of HHP on avocado PPO activity. The lack of information in this field opens a
333 research window to complement already published studies, in which the combined effect
334 of time, pH, temperature or the use of modified atmospheres, for example, on the
335 inactivation of PPO in avocado pulp, in different formats, slices, puree, halves, etc., could
336 be compared.

337 *Radiation treatment*

338 According to the Food and Drugs Administration (FDA), food irradiation is the
339 application of ionizing radiation to food using gamma rays, X-rays or Electron beams (e-
340 beams) (72).

341 Gamma rays are a form of electromagnetic radiation that has no charge or mass (73).
342 They are highly penetrating and have the highest frequencies and energies in the
343 electromagnetic spectrum. The use of gamma irradiators is increasing annually (74).
344 However, this technology is subject to restrictive regulations. In the European Union,
345 Directive 1999/3/EC of the European Parliament and Council establishes a community
346 list of foods and food ingredients that can be treated using ionizing radiation. The only
347 group included in this list is dried aromatic herbs, spices, and vegetable seasonings.
348 However, there are exceptions to certain countries where it is permitted to irradiate fruits,

349 vegetables, meat, and other food groups. On the other hand, several countries can import
350 them as long as they are properly labeled. The maximum doses of irradiation in the food
351 industry is 10 kGy, but for fruits and vegetables, meat, fish, and cereals it is up to 3 kGy
352 (75).

353 In the food industry, the main sources of gamma rays are Cobalt 60 (^{60}Co) and
354 Cesium 137 (^{137}Cs), where ^{60}Co presents certain advantages over the latter. In this
355 sense, ^{60}Co is insoluble in water, which prevents the risk of environmental contamination
356 and generates more energy at a lower initial cost (76). In addition, ^{60}Co is an artificial
357 radionuclide produced from Cobalt 59, a stable non-radioactive metal. Furthermore, ^{60}Co
358 has a relatively long half-life of 5.27 years and undergoes beta decay to Nickel 60 (^{60}Ni),
359 emitting one or two gamma ray photons from a nuclear excited state to reach a stable
360 isotope or ground state of ^{60}Ni (77). According to previously reported studies, the effects
361 of gamma rays from ^{60}Co have been evaluated for food preservation and storage at doses
362 between 1.5 kGy and 2.5 kGy. These studies have shown that irradiation can extend the
363 shelf life of fruits and vegetables by more than 40 days (78,79). However, lower doses
364 could also increase shelf life by inhibiting the growth of microorganisms in nuts, so the
365 dosage can also depend on the food to which it is applied (80).

366 In terms of nutritional value, irradiation can alter the amino acid chains of food
367 proteins, leading to proteins denaturation through the modification of secondary and
368 tertiary structures. This may have both positive and negative effects. On the one hand, it
369 could inhibit enzymes in the food, such as polyphenol oxidase or peroxidase. On the other
370 hand, it can lead to structural changes in the food due to the acceleration of the
371 aforementioned protein denaturation process by altering the amino acid chains through
372 electron transfer. With regard to lipid content, radiation accelerates interrelated processes
373 such as lipid oxidation, the production of hydrogen peroxide and free radicals, and the

374 destruction of antioxidants. Therefore, radiation treatment is not initially recommended
375 for high-fat foods such as avocado fruit (81).

376 Gamma radiation treatment has produced controversial results in avocados. In this
377 sense, doses above 100 Gy caused visual damage to the mesocarp tissue. However, a dose
378 of 150 Gy showed an increase in the number of cells. In contrast, the highest dose, 250
379 Gy, decreased the number of cells, which may be due to the difficulty in counting cells
380 because of the tissue's darkness (82). Another study applied doses lower than 100 Gy and
381 showed that they were effective in reducing PPO activity. The results revealed that this
382 treatment did not affect the sensory parameters, including colour changes compared to
383 the untreated control (83).

384 Nowadays, sources of non-ionizing radiation such as ultraviolet (UV) radiation (400-
385 100 nm) are being studied as a substitute for ionizing treatment. UV radiation is mainly
386 divided into three bands, where UV-A (400-300 nm) and UV-B (320-280) are the longer
387 wavelength and lower energy groups of UV. They are present in sunlight and have some
388 germicidal value (81). In addition, UV-C has the shortest wavelength (200-280 nm) and
389 the highest energy radiation (84,85). UV-C is a well-known antimicrobial agent that can
390 damage the DNA of microorganisms. In recent years, the food industry has been
391 investigating the use of non-thermal treatments, such as UV-C radiation, to extend the
392 shelf-life of food products. UV-C is primarily used for surface disinfection, but it can also
393 increase the shelf life of food products by modifying enzymatic activity through protein
394 structure changes due to photo-oxidation (86). The effect of these rays on molecules
395 suggested doubts about their safety. Currently, food safety agencies such as EFSA and
396 FDA have not found UV-C treatment of food products to be dangerous to humans (75).
397 However, they have not yet established safe doses for this treatment (85).

398 Recently, the use of pulsed light is emerging in the food industry as a new promising
399 method to replace the ionizing radiation methods, which present controversial issues in
400 their application. Pulsed light is the most implemented method for applying UV-C. It
401 generates radiation using a xenon flash lamp, which applies high-speed electronic pulses
402 in a short time and high peak energy (87,88). Some factors that affect the performance of
403 this technology are the number of light sources, the frequency of the pulses and the
404 spectral range of the light flashes (87). This method is effective in the inactivation of
405 enzymes associated with enzymatic browning (38).

406 Studies carried out in food have shown that treatments with UV-C (1 kJ/m²) can
407 reduce the enzymatic browning index, PPO activity, and the loss of phenol and ascorbic
408 acid content in vegetables (84,89). UV-C light treatment has also been studied in avocado
409 fruit. However, it was found to be ineffective in controlling enzymatic browning. It also
410 led to an increase in the total phenolic content due to the stress conditions caused by
411 ultraviolet radiations, which can break the vacuoles where the phenolic compounds are
412 stored in cells (90). Compared with gamma radiation treatment, exposure to UV-C for 5,
413 10, 15, and 20 minutes was less effective in inhibiting PPO activity. In addition, marked
414 colour changes were observed in treated avocados compared with untreated control (83).
415 These results indicate that UV-C is less effective than gamma radiation, possibly because
416 of its lower energy. All of this means that complementary studies are needed to determine
417 the cost-benefit ratio of ionising radiation prior to UV-C due to the high cost of the
418 equipment required to generate the radiation, the difficulty of managing nuclear sources,
419 and the restrictions of its use.

420 *Electromagnetic fields and cold plasma treatment.*

421 Electric fields (EF) are usually used in the food industry as pulsed electric fields
422 (PEF). It uses high-voltage electric waves and high-voltage electric amplitude (10-80
423 kV/cm), in short impulses from microseconds to milliseconds (91,92). Although PEF is
424 the most studied method to apply EF, there are other methods with lower electrical
425 intensity (1-7 V/cm), such as direct current (DC) EF or alternating current (AC) EF,
426 which have been shown to be useful for the treatment of food for human consumption
427 (93,94). In the PEF treatment, the food is placed between two electrodes inside a chamber
428 where it is subjected to electrical pulses. These electrical pulses can modify enzyme
429 activity in three ways. First, by inducing the translation and rotation of enzymes, causing
430 a change in protein conformation; second by absorbing energy from polar groups of
431 proteins, leading to the generation of free radicals that can damage molecular structures;
432 and finally by causing protein aggregation or unfolding, leading to alterations in
433 functional properties and enzyme structure (95). The effectiveness of this method is
434 highly dependent on the composition and physical properties of the food being treated
435 (92). For example, peeled potatoes are more susceptible to electrical treatment than whole
436 potatoes because the skin may act as an electrical insulator, hindering the passage of
437 electricity. Moreover, the vascular traces are highly conductive, providing more potential
438 entry points for the electric current, thus making the peeled potato more susceptible to
439 electric field treatment (96). It has been demonstrated that fruits and vegetables with high
440 water content are more susceptible to the effect of EF because of their better electrical
441 conductivity (Jin et al., 2017). This makes EF a potential method for prolonging shelf-
442 life, especially for temperature-sensitive fruits and vegetables (Z. Zhang et al., 2022).

443 Currently, there is only one article that applies PEF in avocado fruit to promote PPO
444 inhibition. In this sense, the effect of PEF treatment in avocado PPO was studied by
445 Castonera-García et al., where frequencies in the range of 0 to 760 kHz and 18 kV/cm

446 were applied to an extract of the isolated enzyme. The displayed results demonstrated that
447 treatments above 1 kHz were ineffective in keeping the enzyme stable. However, below
448 this frequency, the activity of avocado PPO decreased to 15% of the residual activity. In
449 addition, this treatment kept the temperature constant without contact with the foodstuff,
450 which would be a great advantage of this technology to deal with enzymatic browning in
451 liquid, semi-solid, and solid foods (97).

452 In addition, magnetic fields (MF) are generated by electric current in conductors or
453 by permanent magnets. There are three types according to their behaviour over time:
454 static, oscillating or pulsed. They can also be classified according to their magnetic flux
455 density, measured in Tesla (T), or their frequency, measured in Hz. The effectiveness of
456 MF is conditioned by the physical quantities of the food and the characteristics of the
457 system, such as resistivity, electrical conductivity, thickness, or magnetic susceptibility
458 (98). When other treatments, e.g., vacuum, are used in combination with MF, the
459 composition of the food also plays an important role in influencing the effect of the
460 treatment (99). The main advantage of this method lies in its great depth of penetration
461 into food materials without contact with the food matrix, which makes it possible to treat
462 the inside of food (100). Magnetic fields are often used in combination with other methods
463 for freezing treatment. MF can accelerate the freezing process and prevent the formation
464 of large ice crystals because it induces better alignment of the nuclear and electronic spins
465 of water molecules presents their clumping giving rise small and homogeneous ice
466 crystals (101). Wang et al., 2022 studied the effect of the application of magnetic fields
467 to improve the maintenance of the sensorial characteristics of avocado purée during
468 frozen storage. Under conditions of 50 Hz and 4 mT, it was observed that MF improved
469 the texture characteristics and provided better sensorial qualities compared with the
470 untreated control, thus stopping the deterioration of stored avocado. Moreover, it was

471 found that freezing in combination with MF preserved the total phenol content, probably
472 because of the reduction of PPO activity. These results revealed that MF is a promising
473 technology for improving the shelf life and sensorial qualities of avocado products (102).

474 Finally, Cold Plasma technology (CP) consists in the reactive species produced by the
475 application of an electric current to a gas, causing the ionization of its molecules (87).
476 These reactive species can affect the enzymes present in food and cause their inactivation
477 by free radicals and atomic oxygen-mediated oxidation (103). In the study conducted by
478 Ferreira-Batista et al., plasma was generated with nitrogen by applying an 80 kHz electric
479 field through the electrode inside a processing chamber containing avocado pulp. Plasma
480 was applied for 10, 20, or 30 minutes with a gas flow of 10, 20, or 30 ml/min with or
481 without pulp lime extract, and hence, comparing, also, the effect of pH in the PPO
482 inhibition after applying this methodology. The treatment increased the activity of PPO
483 in all the groups, resulting in a higher level of brown colour in avocado pulp, except when
484 20 ml/min and 20-30 min with pulp lime extract were applied. During these conditions,
485 PPO activity decreased by 5% and 11%, respectively. These outcomes may be explained
486 probably by the reduction of pH and the longer treatment time. On the other hand, the
487 increased activity in almost all the groups may be attributed to the breaking of cell walls
488 caused by the cold plasma effect, which allowed enzymes and their substrates to interact
489 with each other. However, all the groups experienced a positive reduction of peroxidase
490 (POD) activity, probably due to possible destruction of the heme cofactor by reactive
491 plasma species (104). Although the inhibition of PPO is less compared with other physical
492 methods, this study demonstrated the potential of cold plasma treatment to extend the
493 shelf life of avocado pulp. However, the small number of published works in which cold
494 plasma is applied does not give a clear idea about the usefulness and applicability of this

495 technique for the reduction of PPO activity. Therefore, more extensive research is
496 required to determine its effectiveness on avocado pulp.

497 *Ozone treatment*

498 Ozone is a triatomic form of oxygen and a powerful oxidant that can inhibit enzymatic
499 activities by the oxidation of protein structures, leading to a conformational change of
500 their structures by the effect of ozone or other reactive species. Thus, this technology can
501 preserve the firmness of fruits during storage and extend their shelf-life (105,106).
502 According to the FDA, ozone is produced by passing electrical discharges or ionizing
503 radiation through air. This gas was designated as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS)
504 by the relevant authorities (107). Furthermore, it was classified as a safe additive in the
505 treatment, storage, and processing of foods in Title 21 of the Code of Federal Regulations,
506 Part 173, since 2001 by the FDA and subsequently amended in 2023 (108). This treatment
507 has been used to evaluate the shelf life of foods such as coriander, mushrooms, and
508 sugarcane. All these studies confirmed that the application of gaseous ozone was effective
509 in suppressing PPO activity, and the enzymes involved in chlorophyll degradation were
510 also inhibited, maintaining the phenolic and flavonoid content, antioxidant capacity, and
511 nutritional value. These results show that ozone treatment may be a potential technology
512 for extending the shelf life of foods (109–111).

513 In a study carried out in fresh cut avocado fruit, an ozone treatment was used in
514 different doses (10, 20, and 40 ppm) for 15, 30 and 45 minutes respectively. Later,
515 avocado fruits were stored for 1 month at 5°C with 85-90% of relative humidity. The
516 results showed that all the groups treated with ozone increased their PPO activity
517 compared with the untreated control. In contrast, the total phenol content was better
518 preserved in the group treated with 40 ppm ozone for 45 minutes. Although the

519 application of this technique is straightforward, the contradictory results and the paucity
520 of previously published work make it difficult to discern the effectiveness of this
521 treatment on avocado PPO inhibition (112).

522 *Packaging and storage conditions*

523 Modified Atmosphere Packaging (MAP) is a strategy used to enhance the quality of
524 stored food by controlling the interaction between the respiration of the food and the
525 transfer of gasses through the packaging. This is achieved by combining different
526 proportions of gasses such as nitrogen (N₂), oxygen (O₂), and carbon dioxide (CO₂), as
527 well as considering factors such as the packaging material, respiration rate, and gas
528 diffusion through package microperforations. In this sense, MAP conditions that involve
529 low O₂ and high CO₂ levels can inhibit or delay the PPO reaction by reducing O₂ in the
530 surrounding atmosphere. In addition, MAP can be used in combination with other
531 methods, such as cold storage or the use of additives, to improve its effectiveness in
532 extending the shelf life of food (113,114).

533 Vacuum cooling storage (VC) is a mixed physical method used to control the
534 deterioration of fruits and vegetables. This technology is based on a rapid evaporative
535 cooling method that can be used for foods with low water content or whose structure will
536 not be damaged by the removal of water from their matrix (115). This technology is based
537 on the principle of lowering the pressure to decrease the boiling point of water and create
538 a vacuum. In this way, the reduction of pressure inside the vacuum chamber ensures that
539 the energy required for evaporation of the water is provided in the form of latent heat of
540 evaporation from the product itself (116). The control of enzymatic browning with this
541 technology in vegetables such as mushroom has already been studied, and the results

542 showed an effective reduction of colour changes associated with enzymatic browning
543 (115).

544 Studies have confirmed the positive effect of low oxygen modified atmospheres in
545 delaying ripening and deteriorating avocado fruit (117). Soliva et al. showed that high
546 nitrogen atmospheres, even with additives such as ascorbic acid, sorbic acid, or EDTA,
547 were more useful in reducing avocado PPO activity than vacuum storage or atmospheric
548 air packaging. Additionally, the research carried out by Gerdes & Parrino-Lowe found no
549 effect on PPO activity when avocados were packaged in controlled atmospheres, even
550 atmospheric air, vacuum, or commercial gas mixtures (118), but although there was no
551 effect on enzymatic inhibition, this storage treatment could slow down the deterioration
552 of this fruit (119). These results show that modifying the packaging conditions may be
553 useful in increasing the shelf-life of avocado fruit and suggest a method in which the
554 conditions could be easily varied to optimize the improvement of sensory characteristics
555 in the products through multiple storage options.

556

557 **Conclusions**

558 Avocado is a fruit whose shelf life can be easily compromised due to its nutritional
559 composition and undergoes important organoleptic changes, mainly PPO-induced
560 enzymatic browning, leading to consumer rejection. The management and control of
561 these biochemical processes is particularly important in maintaining the quality of
562 avocado pulp and derivative products. In this sense, physical technologies have the
563 potential to control enzymatic browning by reducing, fully or partially, the activity of the
564 enzyme PPO. However, these methods need to be refined to achieve the best results in
565 inhibiting PPO while preserving the sensory properties as much as possible. Heat
566 treatment is the most used and effective technology, but it gives sensorial changes to food.

567 Although ultrasound provided promising results on avocado PPO inhibition, ultrasounds
568 systems are still difficult to scale it up in the agri-food industry. Therefore, to address
569 these issues, the food industry is developing novel non-thermal technologies that
570 effectively extend the shelf life of avocados.

571 Therefore, HPP represents the most promising method for the substitution of heat
572 treatment in avocado products because of it has no effect on the sensory profile of avocado
573 products. Nevertheless, the optimal pressure range and treatment duration remain under
574 discussion because of the inherent differences between avocado products.
575 Electromagnetic treatment is also being explored for its potential use in the food industry.
576 However, an effective method and application equipment are required for the future
577 development of this technology in the food industry. Conversely, while the application of
578 radiation is effective in reducing PPO activity, further optimization is required because
579 of the difficulty in managing radioactive sources. Finally, the modification of the
580 composition of the atmospheres or vacuum environments in the packaging represent
581 another promising alternative to increase the shelf life of avocado products. This approach
582 has already been implemented in the food industry, but the conditions of the atmosphere
583 must be optimized for avocado fruit. Future studies should concentrate on assessing the
584 combined impact of these technologies, with a view to identify potential synergies
585 between them.

586 The results of the studies compiled in this review indicate that the majority of the
587 physical methods examined could be effective in PPO inhibition. Nevertheless, a
588 convenient standardization of the analytical methods for the evaluation of enzymatic
589 browning is necessary with the aim of facilitating a representative comparison between
590 technologies. At present, the most commonly used methods for the evaluation of PPO
591 activity are colorimetric approaches or *in vitro* assays based on spectrophotometric

592 methods, making it difficult to compare results between techniques. Furthermore, the lack
593 of recent studies on avocado means that further extensive research is needed to verify and
594 optimize these novel technologies on the effect on enzymatic browning without
595 compromising the organoleptic quality and safety of the products obtained.

596 **Disclosure statement**

597 The author declares there is no conflict of interest.

598 **Funding and acknowledgements**

599 V.J.T. is gratefully acknowledges for the FPU grant (FPU22/00680) funded by
600 Spanish Ministry of Universities. F.J.L.J. thanks to the grant FJC2020-044298-I funded
601 by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by European Union NextGeneration
602 EU/PRTR. M.L.C.G. thanks her contract RYC2021-032119-I founded by
603 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and NextGenerationEU/PRTR.

604

605 **References**

- 606 1. Thomas GA, Paradell Gil T, Müller CT, Rogers HJ, Berger CN. From field to
607 plate: How do bacterial enteric pathogens interact with ready-to-eat fruit and
608 vegetables, causing disease outbreaks? *Food Microbiol* [Internet].
609 2024;117:104389. doi: 10.1016/j.fm.2023.104389.
- 610 2. Wei X, Wang J, Wang Y, Zhao Y, Long Y, Tan B, Li QX, Dong Z, Wan X.
611 Dietary fiber and polyphenols from whole grains: effects on the gut and health
612 improvements. *Food Funct*. 2024; doi: 10.1039/d4fo00715h.
- 613 3. Wallace TC, Bailey RL, Blumberg JB, Burton-Freeman B, Chen CO, Crowe-
614 White KM, Drewnowski A, Hooshmand S, Johnson E, Lewis R, et al. Fruits,
615 vegetables, and health: A comprehensive narrative, umbrella review of the
616 science and recommendations for enhanced public policy to improve intake. *Crit*
617 *Rev Food Sci Nutr* [Internet]. 2020;60:2174–2211. doi:
618 10.1080/10408398.2019.1632258.
- 619 4. FAO. Cultivos y productos de ganadería [Internet]. 2023. Available from:
620 <https://www.fao.org/faostat/es/#data/QCL>.
- 621 5. Ministerio de Agricultura (España). Alimentacion en España 2023 [Internet].
622 MERCASA-DI. Editorial MIC, editor. 2023. Available from:
623 [https://www.mercasa.es/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/ALIMENTACION-EN-](https://www.mercasa.es/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/ALIMENTACION-EN-ESPANA_2023.pdf)
624 [ESPANA_2023.pdf](https://www.mercasa.es/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/ALIMENTACION-EN-ESPANA_2023.pdf).
- 625 6. Ford NA, Spagnuolo P, Kraft J, Bauer E. Nutritional Composition of Hass
626 Avocado Pulp. *Foods* [Internet]. 2023;12:2516. doi: 10.3390/foods12132516.
- 627 7. Figueroa JG, Borrás-Linares I, Lozano-Sánchez J, Segura-Carretero A.

- 628 Comprehensive identification of bioactive compounds of avocado peel by liquid
629 chromatography coupled to ultra-high-definition accurate-mass Q-TOF. *Food*
630 *Chem* [Internet]. 2018;245:707–716. doi: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.12.011.
631 Cited in: : PMID: 29287430.
- 632 8. Alkaltham MS, Uslu N, Özcan MM, Salamatullah AM, Mohamed Ahmed IA,
633 Hayat K. Effect of drying process on oil, phenolic composition and antioxidant
634 activity of avocado (cv. Hass) fruits harvested at two different maturity stages.
635 *LWT*. 2021;148. doi: 10.1016/j.lwt.2021.111716.
- 636 9. Babiker EE, Mohamed Ahmed IA, Uslu N, Özcan MM, Al Juhaimi F, Ghafoor
637 K, Almusallam IA. Influence of drying methods on bioactive properties, fatty
638 acids and phenolic compounds of different parts of ripe and unripe avocado
639 fruits. *J Oleo Sci*. 2021;70:589–598. doi: 10.5650/jos.ess20343. Cited in: :
640 PMID: 33692245.
- 641 10. López-Cobo A, Gómez-Caravaca AM, Pasini F, Caboni MF, Segura-Carretero A,
642 Fernández-Gutiérrez A. HPLC-DAD-ESI-QTOF-MS and HPLC-FLD-MS as
643 valuable tools for the determination of phenolic and other polar compounds in the
644 edible part and by-products of avocado. *LWT*. 2016;73:505–513. doi:
645 10.1016/j.lwt.2016.06.049.
- 646 11. Serrano-García I, Domínguez-García J, Hurtado-Fernández E, González-
647 Fernández JJ, Hormaza JI, Beiro-Valenzuela MG, Monasterio R, Pedreschi R,
648 Olmo-García L, Carrasco-Pancorbo A. Assessing the RP-LC-MS-Based
649 Metabolic Profile of Hass Avocados Marketed in Europe from Different
650 Geographical Origins (Peru, Chile, and Spain) over the Whole Season. *Plants*.
651 2023;12. doi: 10.3390/plants12163004.

- 652 12. Villa-Rodriguez JA, Yahia EM, González-León A, Ifie I, Robles-Zepeda RE,
653 Domínguez-Avila JA, González-Aguilar GA. Ripening of ‘Hass’ avocado
654 mesocarp alters its phytochemical profile and the in vitro cytotoxic activity of its
655 methanolic extracts. *South African J Bot.* 2020;128:1–8. doi:
656 10.1016/j.sajb.2019.09.020.
- 657 13. Nguyen TVL, Nguyen QD, Nguyen TTD, Nguyen PBD. Effects of infrared
658 drying conditions and maltodextrin addition on some physicochemical
659 characteristics of avocado (*Persea Americana*) pulp powder. *Appl Sci.* 2021;11.
660 doi: 10.3390/app112411803.
- 661 14. Kaya ED, Bağci O. Purification and biochemical characterization of polyphenol
662 oxidase extracted from Kirmizi Kismis grape (*Vitis vinifera* L.). *J Food Biochem.*
663 2021;45. doi: 10.1111/jfbc.13627. Cited: in: : PMID: 33522611.
- 664 15. Moon KM, Kwon E Bin, Lee B, Kim CY. Recent Trends in Controlling the
665 Enzymatic Browning of Fruit and Vegetable Products. *Molecules.* MDPI AG;
666 2020.
- 667 16. Arnold M, Gramza-Michałowska A. Enzymatic browning in apple products and
668 its inhibition treatments: A comprehensive review. *Compr Rev Food Sci Food*
669 *Saf [Internet].* 2022 [cited 2024 Apr 18];21:5038–5076. doi: 10.1111/1541-
670 4337.13059. Cited: in: : PMID: 36301625.
- 671 17. Zhang S. Recent Advances of Polyphenol Oxidases in Plants. *Molecules*
672 *[Internet].* 2023 [cited 2024 Apr 18];28. doi: 10.3390/molecules28052158. Cited:
673 in: : PMID: 36903403.
- 674 18. Sui X, Meng Z, Dong T, Fan X, Wang Q. Enzymatic browning and polyphenol
675 oxidase control strategies. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* Elsevier Ltd; 2023.

- 676 19. Benaceur F, Chaibi R, Berrabah F, Neifar A, Leboukh M, Benaceur K, Nouioua
677 W, Rezzoug A, Bouazzara H, Gouzi H, et al. Purification and characterization of
678 latent polyphenol oxidase from truffles (*Terfezia arenaria*). *Int J Biol Macromol*.
679 2020;145:885–893. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.09.126. Cited: in: : PMID:
680 31778703.
- 681 20. Sajjad N, Ahmad MS, Mahmood RT, Tariq M, Asad MJ, Irum S, Andleeb A,
682 Riaz A, Ahmed D. Purification and characterization of novel isoforms of the
683 polyphenol oxidase from *Malus domestica* fruit pulp. *PLoS One*. 2023;18. doi:
684 10.1371/journal.pone.0276041. Cited: in: : PMID: 37624797.
- 685 21. Torres A, Aguilar-Osorio G, Camacho M, Basurto F, Navarro-Ocana A.
686 Characterization of polyphenol oxidase from purple sweet potato (*Ipomoea*
687 *batatas* L. Lam) and its affinity towards acylated anthocyanins and caffeoylquinic
688 acid derivatives. *Food Chem*. 2021;356. doi: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.129709.
689 Cited: in: : PMID: 33823400.
- 690 22. Azzouzi N, Britel MR, Maurady A. Characterization of Polyphenol Oxidase
691 (PPO) from Blackberry Thorny Wild *Rubus Fruticosus* and its Inhibition using
692 Natural Extracts. *Curr Res Nutr Food Sci*. 2022;10:1205–1221. doi:
693 10.12944/CRNFSJ.10.3.33.
- 694 23. Fuentes Campo A, Sancho MI, Melo G, Dávila YA, Gasull E. In vitro and in
695 vivo inhibition of Hass avocado polyphenol oxidase enzymatic browning by
696 paeonol, β -cyclodextrin, and paeonol: β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex. *J Biosci*
697 *Bioeng*. 2019;127:703–709. doi: 10.1016/j.jbiosc.2018.11.009. Cited: in: : PMID:
698 30573385.
- 699 24. Huang J, Gao X, Su L, Liu X, Guo L, Zhang Z, Zhao D, Hao J. Purification,

700 characterization and inactivation kinetics of polyphenol oxidase extracted from
701 *Cistanche deserticola*. *Planta*. 2023;257. doi: 10.1007/s00425-023-04118-y.
702 Cited in: : PMID: 36944703.

703 25. Razavi MS, Golmohammadi A, Nematollahzadeh A, Ghanbari A, Davari M,
704 Rovera C, Carullo D, Farris S. Impact of Bacterial Cellulose Nanocrystals-
705 Gelatin/Cinnamon Essential Oil Emulsion Coatings on the Quality Attributes of
706 ‘Red Delicious’ Apples. *Coatings*. 2022;12. doi: 10.3390/coatings12060741.

707 26. Shah HMS, Singh Z, Hasan MU, Kaur J, Afrifa-Yamoah E, Woodward A.
708 Melatonin application suppresses oxidative stress and maintains fruit quality of
709 cold stored ‘Esperanza’ raspberries by regulating antioxidant system. *Postharvest
710 Biol Technol*. 2024;207. doi: 10.1016/j.postharvbio.2023.112597.

711 27. Magri A, Cice D, Capriolo G, Petriccione M. Effects of Ascorbic Acid and
712 Melatonin Treatments on Antioxidant System in Fresh-Cut Avocado Fruits
713 During Cold Storage. *Food Bioprocess Technol*. 2022;15:2468–2482. doi:
714 10.1007/s11947-022-02892-3.

715 28. Singh B, Suri K, Shevkani K, Kaur A, Kaur A, Singh N. Enzymatic browning of
716 fruit and vegetables: A review. *Enzym Food Technol Improv Innov*. Springer
717 Singapore; 2018. p. 73–78.

718 29. Shah HMS, Khan AS, Ali S. Pre-storage kojic acid application delays pericarp
719 browning and maintains antioxidant activities of litchi fruit. *Postharvest Biol
720 Technol*. 2017;132:154–161. doi: 10.1016/j.postharvbio.2017.06.004.

721 30. Adhikary T, Gill PPS, Jawandha SK, Kaur N, Sinha A. Exogenous application of
722 oxalic acid improves the storage quality of Asian pears (*Patharnakh*) by
723 regulating physiological and biochemical changes. *Acta Physiol Plant*. 2024;46.

- 724 doi: 10.1007/s11738-023-03624-6.
- 725 31. Zawawi NAF, Hazmi NAM, How MS, Kantono K, Silva FVM, Sulaiman A.
726 Thermal, High Pressure, and Ultrasound Inactivation of Various Fruit Cultivars'
727 Polyphenol Oxidase: Kinetic Inactivation Models and Estimation of Treatment
728 Energy Requirement. *Appl. Sci. MDPI*; 2022.
- 729 32. Jha PK, Chapleau N, Meyers PE, Pathier D, Le-Bail A. Can cryogenic freezing
730 preserve the quality of fruit matrices during long-term storage compared to the
731 mechanical method? *Appl Food Res.* 2024;4. doi: 10.1016/j.afres.2023.100374.
- 732 33. Singhal P, Satya S, Naik SN. Blanching: A sustainable and effective treatment
733 for extending shelf life of bamboo shoots. *Food Chem Adv.* 2023;2. doi:
734 10.1016/j.focha.2022.100179.
- 735 34. Wang R, Liu J, Zhang J, Li G, Ding S. Effect of thermal blanching on the
736 inactivation kinetics of polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase in lily bulb, and the
737 functional properties of its flours. *J Food Meas Charact.* 2023;17:615–626. doi:
738 10.1007/s11694-022-01658-x.
- 739 35. Mandha J, Shumoy H, Matemu AO, Raes K. Characterization of fruit juices and
740 effect of pasteurization and storage conditions on their microbial,
741 physicochemical, and nutritional quality. *Food Biosci.* 2023;51. doi:
742 10.1016/j.fbio.2022.102335.
- 743 36. Maryana D, Suriani, Maruddin F, Dianasari U, Syaggaf AW, Prahesti KI.
744 Organoleptic Quality of Pasteurized Milk with Addition of Various
745 Concentrations of Beetroot Extract (*Beta vulgaris L*) and Different Pasteurization
746 Methods. *AIP Conf Proc. American Institute of Physics Inc.*; 2023.

- 747 37. Zou W, Niu H, Yi J, Zhou L. Passion fruit juicing with or without seeds treated
748 by high-pressure processing and thermal pasteurization: Effects on the storage
749 stability of enzymes and quality properties. *Innov Food Sci Emerg Technol*.
750 2024;91. doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2023.103554.
- 751 38. Li W, Liu Z, Wang H, Yuan J, Zheng Y, Duan L, Tang Y, Jiang Y, Li X, Jiang
752 Y. Heat shock pretreatment and low temperature fluctuation cold storage
753 maintains flesh quality and retards watercore dissipation of watercored “Fuji”
754 apples. *Sci Hortic (Amsterdam)*. 2024;323. doi: 10.1016/j.scienta.2023.112492.
- 755 39. Vanini LSL, Kwiatkowski A, Clemente E, Kwiatkowski A, Clemente E,
756 Kwiatkowski A, Clemente E. Polyphenoloxidase and peroxidase in avocado pulp
757 (*Persea americana* Mill.). *Ciência e Tecnol Aliment [Internet]*. 2010 [cited 2024
758 Apr 18];30:525–531. doi: 10.1590/S0101-20612010000200036.
- 759 40. Weemaes CA, Ludikhuyze LR, Van Den Broeck I, Hendrickx ME, Tobback PP.
760 Activity, electrophoretic characteristics and heat inactivation of
761 polyphenoloxidases from apples, avocados, grapes, pears and plums. *LWT*
762 [Internet]. 1998;31:44–49. doi: 10.1006/fstl.1997.0302.
- 763 41. Anusha R, Bishnoi JP. The impact of various pre-treatments on the
764 physiochemical attributes and storage stability of *Persea americana*. *Vegetos*
765 [Internet]. 2023;36:181–187. doi: 10.1007/s42535-022-00506-z.
- 766 42. Salvador-Reyes R, Paucar-Menacho LM. Optimization of the blanching time and
767 temperature in the manufacture of Hass avocado pulp using low quality discarded
768 fruits. *Brazilian J Food Technol [Internet]*. 2019;22. doi: 10.1590/1981-
769 6723.24418.
- 770 43. Donadon JR, Durigan JF, Morgado CMAA, Durigan MFBB. Chilling injury in

771 avocados and its prevention with thermal treatment. *Acta Hort* [Internet].
772 International Society for Horticultural Science; 2012. p. 747–754. Available
773 from: [https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84872174323&doi=10.17660%2Factahortic.2012.934.98&partnerID=40&md5=7c245437fef75a0605398b5e216c6afb)
774 [84872174323&doi=10.17660%2Factahortic.2012.934.98&partnerID=40&md5=](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84872174323&doi=10.17660%2Factahortic.2012.934.98&partnerID=40&md5=7c245437fef75a0605398b5e216c6afb)
775 [7c245437fef75a0605398b5e216c6afb](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84872174323&doi=10.17660%2Factahortic.2012.934.98&partnerID=40&md5=7c245437fef75a0605398b5e216c6afb).

776 44. Wu C-TCT, Roan S-FSF, Hsiung TCT-C, Chen I-ZIZ, Shyr J-JJJ, Wakana A.
777 Effect of harvest maturity and heat pretreatment on the quality of low
778 temperature storage avocados in Taiwan. *J Fac Agric Kyushu Univ* [Internet].
779 2011;56:255–262. doi: 10.5109/20318.

780 45. Weemaes CA, Ludikhuyze LR, Van Den Broeck I, Hendrickx ME. Effect of pH
781 on Pressure and Thermal Inactivation of Avocado Polyphenol Oxidase: A Kinetic
782 Study. *J Agric Food Chem* [Internet]. 1998;46:2785–2792. doi:
783 10.1021/jf970902s.

784 46. Albahr Z, Al-Ghamdi S, Tang J, Sablani SS. Pressure-Assisted Thermal
785 Sterilization and Storage Stability of Avocado Puree in High Barrier Polymeric
786 Packaging. *Food Bioprocess Technol* [Internet]. 2022;15:2616–2628. doi:
787 10.1007/s11947-022-02904-2.

788 47. Sarantakou P, Andreou V, Paraskevopoulou E, Dermesonlouoglou EK, Taoukis
789 P. Quality Determination of a High-Pressure Processed Avocado Puree-Based
790 Smoothie Beverage. *Beverages* [Internet]. 2023;9. doi:
791 10.3390/beverages9020038.

792 48. Cao H, Wang X, Liu J, Sun Z, Yu Z, Battino M, El-Seedi H, Guan X.
793 Mechanistic insights into the changes of enzyme activity in food processing
794 under microwave irradiation. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* John Wiley and

- 795 Sons Inc; 2023. p. 2465–2487.
- 796 49. Franco RR, Ojeda GA, Rompato KM, Sgroppo SC. Effects of short-wave
797 ultraviolet light, ultrasonic and microwave treatments on banana puree during
798 refrigerated storage. *Food Sci Technol Int.* 2023;29:50–61. doi:
799 10.1177/10820132211058444. Cited: in: : PMID: 34779305.
- 800 50. Zhang C, Lyu X, Aadil RM, Tong Y, Zhao W, Yang R. Microwave heating
801 instead of blanching to produce low-fat French fries. *Innov Food Sci Emerg*
802 *Technol.* 2023;84. doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2023.103298.
- 803 51. Zhou L, Tey CY, Bingol G, Balaban MO, Cai S. Effect of different microwave
804 power levels on inactivation of PPO and PME and also on quality changes of
805 peach puree. *Curr Res Food Sci.* 2022;5:41–48. doi: 10.1016/j.crf.2021.12.006.
- 806 52. Ospina S, Ortiz DL, Orrego CE. Enzymatic Browning and Color Evolution in
807 Frozen Storage of Two Kinds of Minimally Processed Avocado Puree. *Int J Food*
808 *Eng [Internet].* 2019;15. doi: 10.1515/ijfe-2018-0431.
- 809 53. Guzmán GR, Dorantes AL, Hernández UH, Hernández SH, Ortiz A, Mora ER.
810 Effect of zinc and copper chloride on the color of avocado puree heated with
811 microwaves. *Innov Food Sci Emerg Technol [Internet].* 2002;3:47–53. doi:
812 10.1016/S1466-8564(01)00053-4.
- 813 54. Kutlu N, Pandiselvam R, Saka I, Kamiloglu A, Sahni P, Kothakota A. Impact of
814 different microwave treatments on food texture. *J. Texture Stud.* John Wiley and
815 Sons Inc; 2022. p. 709–736.
- 816 55. Anju T, Saritha GNG, Ramchiary N, Kumar A. Assessing the impact of different
817 cooking methods on nutrients, phytochemicals and antioxidant activity of

- 818 traditional food plants. *Food Chem Adv.* 2024;100677. doi:
819 10.1016/j.focha.2024.100677.
- 820 56. Gao Q, Wang J, Ding T, Song F, Jin G, Raghavan V, Song W, Song C.
821 Comparative evaluation of drying characteristics and antioxidant quality of
822 raspberry by different drying methods. *J Food Process Eng.* 2023;46. doi:
823 10.1111/jfpe.14410.
- 824 57. Rathnakumar K, Kalaivendan RGT, Eazhumalai G, Raja Charles AP, Verma P,
825 Rustagi S, Bharti S, Kothakota A, Siddiqui SA, Manuel Lorenzo J, et al.
826 Applications of ultrasonication on food enzyme inactivation- recent review report
827 (2017–2022). *Ultrason. Sonochem.* Elsevier B.V.; 2023.
- 828 58. Chandrapala J, Oliver C, Kentish S, Ashokkumar M. Ultrasonics in food
829 processing. *Ultrason. Sonochem.* Elsevier B.V.; 2012. p. 975–983.
- 830 59. Kalsi BS, Singh S, Alam MS, Bhatia S. Application of thermosonication for
831 guava juice processing: Impacts on bioactive, microbial, enzymatic and quality
832 attributes. *Ultrason Sonochem.* 2023;99. doi: 10.1016/j.ultsonch.2023.106595.
833 Cited: in : PMID: 37699293.
- 834 60. Restrepo S. AM, Restrepo D. AM, Fuentes M, Durango M, Millán L de J,
835 Londoño JA, Ochoa S. The evaluation of the potential usage of the ultrasound
836 technology of the microbiological and physicochemical quality of the avocado
837 pulp. *Vitae.* 2015;23:S774–S778.
- 838 61. Bi X, Hemar Y, Balaban MO, Liao X. The effect of ultrasound on particle size,
839 color, viscosity and polyphenol oxidase activity of diluted avocado puree.
840 *Ultrason Sonochem* [Internet]. 2015;27:567–575. doi:
841 10.1016/j.ultsonch.2015.04.011.

- 842 62. Wang W, Yang P, Rao L, Zhao L, Wu X, Wang Y, Liao X. Effect of high
843 hydrostatic pressure processing on the structure, functionality, and nutritional
844 properties of food proteins: A review. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* John
845 Wiley and Sons Inc; 2022. p. 4640–4682.
- 846 63. Navarro-Baez JE, Martínez LM, Welti-Chanes J, Buitimea-Cantúa G V.,
847 Escobedo-Avellaneda Z. High Hydrostatic Pressure to Increase the Biosynthesis
848 and Extraction of Phenolic Compounds in Food: A Review. *Molecules.* MDPI;
849 2022.
- 850 64. Gutiérrez ÁL, Rico D, Ronda F, Caballero PA, Martín-Diana AB. The
851 Application of High-Hydrostatic-Pressure Processing to Improve the Quality of
852 Baked Products: A Review. *Foods.* Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
853 (MDPI); 2024.
- 854 65. D'Arrigo M, Delgado-Adámez J, Rocha-Pimienta J, Valdés-Sánchez ME,
855 Ramírez-Bernabé MR. Integral Use of Red Wine Pomace after Hydrostatic High
856 Pressure: Application of Two Consecutive Cycles of Treatment. *Foods.* 2024;13.
857 doi: 10.3390/foods13010149.
- 858 66. Chakraborty S, Kaushik N, Rao PS, Mishra HN. High-pressure inactivation of
859 enzymes: A review on its recent applications on fruit purees and juices. *Compr.*
860 *Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* Blackwell Publishing Inc.; 2014. p. 578–596.
- 861 67. López-Malo A, Palou E, Barbosa-Cánovas G V, Welti-Chanes J, Swanson BG.
862 Polyphenoloxidase activity and color changes during storage of high hydrostatic
863 pressure treated avocado puree. *Food Res Int [Internet].* 1998;31:549–556. doi:
864 10.1016/S0963-9969(99)00028-9.
- 865 68. Weemaes CA, Ludikhuyze LR, Van Den Broeck I, Hendrickx ME. High pressure

- 866 inactivation of polyphenoloxidases. *J Food Sci* [Internet]. 1998;63:873–877. doi:
867 10.1111/j.1365-2621.1998.tb17917.x.
- 868 69. Palou E, Hernández-Salgado C, López-Malo A, Barbosa-Cánovas G V, Swanson
869 BG, Welti-Chanes J. High pressure-processed guacamole. *Innov Food Sci Emerg*
870 *Technol* [Internet]. 2000;1:69–75. doi: 10.1016/S1466-8564(99)00002-8.
- 871 70. Weemaes CA, Ludikhuyze LR, Van Den Broeck I, Hendrickx ME. Kinetics of
872 combined pressure-temperature inactivation of avocado polyphenoloxidase.
873 *Biotechnol Bioeng*. 1998;60:292–300. doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-
874 0290(19981105)60:3<292::AID-BIT4>3.0.CO;2-C. Cited in: : PMID:
875 10099431.
- 876 71. Woolf AB, Wibisono R, Farr J, Hallett I, Richter L, Oey I, Wohlers M, Zhou J,
877 Fletcher GC, Requejo-Jackman C. Effect of high pressure processing on avocado
878 slices. *Innov Food Sci Emerg Technol* [Internet]. 2013;18:65–73. doi:
879 10.1016/j.ifset.2013.02.011.
- 880 72. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Food Irradiation: What you need to know.
881 *Food Facts* [Internet]. 2016;1–2.
- 882 73. Consejo de Seguridad Nuclear. Las radiaciones: Radiaciones ionizantes. Csn
883 [Internet]. 2019;1–5.
- 884 74. Chmielewski AG. Radiation technologies: The future is today. *Radiat Phys Chem*
885 [Internet]. 2023;213:111233. doi: 10.1016/j.radphyschem.2023.111233.
- 886 75. EFSA. Statement summarising the Conclusions and Recommendations from the
887 Opinions on the Safety of Irradiation of Food adopted by the BIOHAZ and CEF
888 Panels. *EFSA J*. 2011;9. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2107.

- 889 76. Chaudhary S, Kumar S, Kumar V, Singh B, Dhiman A. Irradiation: A tool for the
890 sustainability of fruit and vegetable supply chain-Advancements and future
891 trends. *Radiat Phys Chem* [Internet]. 2024;217:111511. doi:
892 10.1016/j.radphyschem.2024.111511.
- 893 77. Nave CR. Beta Decay Examples: Cobalt-60 [Internet]. Hyperphysics. 2017.
894 Available from: <http://hyperphysics.phy-astr.gsu.edu/hbase/Nuclear/betaex.html>.
- 895 78. Hussain PR, Rather SA, Suradkar PP, Ayob O. Gamma irradiation treatment of
896 quince fruit (*Cydonia oblonga* Mill): effect on post-harvest retention of storage
897 quality and inhibition of fungal decay. *J Radiat Res Appl Sci*. 2019;12:118–131.
898 doi: 10.1080/16878507.2019.1618588.
- 899 79. Wang G, Gao J, Lyu C, Meng X, Yue X. Effects of $^{60}\text{Co}\gamma$ irradiation on storage
900 quality and physiology of fresh hazelnut fruits. *J Food Process Preserv*. 2022;46.
901 doi: 10.1111/jfpp.17251.
- 902 80. Edae B. Food Irradiation - An Effective Technology for Food Safety and
903 Security. *Food Sci Nutr Technol*. 2023;8:1–6. doi: 10.23880/fsnt-16000312.
- 904 81. Lima F, Vieira K, Santos M, Mendes de Souza P. Effects of Radiation
905 Technologies on Food Nutritional Quality. *Descr Food Sci*. IntechOpen; 2018.
- 906 82. Arévalo L, Bustos ME, Saucedo Veloz C. Changes in the vascular tissue of fresh
907 Hass avocados treated with cobalt 60. *Agrociencia* [Internet]. 2002;36:667–673.
- 908 83. Daiuto ER, Russo VC, Vietes RL, Fumes JGF, Vileigas DF, Smith RE. Stability
909 of a product prepared with “Fuerte” avocados exposed to gamma and UV-C
910 radiation. *J Food Process Preserv* [Internet]. 2014;38:1999–2005. doi:
911 10.1111/jfpp.12176.

- 912 84. He X, Zhong J, Wei R, Li H, Li J, Ren Y, Zhai X, Hu W, Guan W. Enhancement
913 of quality and self-defense capacity of *Agaricus bisporus* by UV-C treatment. *J*
914 *Sci Food Agric.* 2024;104:400–408. doi: 10.1002/jsfa.12932. Cited in : PMID:
915 37598381.
- 916 85. Tchoukouang RD, Lima AR, Quintino AC, Cristofoli NL, Vieira MC. UV-C
917 Light: A Promising Preservation Technology for Vegetable-Based Nonsolid
918 Food Products. *Foods.* Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI);
919 2023.
- 920 86. Martínez del-Pozo Á, García-Linares S. Structural and Functional Analysis of
921 Water Soluble and Membrane Proteins. Use of Nanodiscs. [Internet]. Univ.
922 Complut. Madrid. 2021 [cited 2024 Apr 18]. Available from:
923 [https://www.ucm.es/otrien/complutransfer-structural-and-functional-analysis-of-](https://www.ucm.es/otrien/complutransfer-structural-and-functional-analysis-of-water-soluble-and-membrane-proteins)
924 [water-soluble-and-membrane-proteins.](https://www.ucm.es/otrien/complutransfer-structural-and-functional-analysis-of-water-soluble-and-membrane-proteins)
- 925 87. Obileke KC, Onyeaka H, Miri T, Nwabor OF, Hart A, Al-Sharify ZT, Al-Najjar
926 S, Anumudu C. Recent advances in radio frequency, pulsed light, and cold
927 plasma technologies for food safety. *J. Food Process Eng.* John Wiley and Sons
928 Inc; 2022.
- 929 88. Singh H, Blennow A, Gupta AD, Kaur P, Dhillon B, Sodhi NS, Dubey PK.
930 Pulsed light, Pulsed Electric Field and Cold plasma modification of Starches:
931 Technological Advancements & Effects on Functional Properties. *J. Food Meas.*
932 *Charact.* Springer; 2022. p. 4092–4109.
- 933 89. Lemos ML, Gutiérrez DR, Farías MJ, Rodríguez S del C. Effect of UV-C
934 treatments on quality and browning-related enzyme activity of fresh-cut eggplant
935 (*Solanum melongena* L.) during cold storage. *J Food Process Preserv.* 2022;46.

- 936 doi: 10.1111/jfpp.16986.
- 937 90. Tremocoldi MA, Daiuto ÉR, Vieites RL, de Alencar SM. Antioxidant Capacity,
938 Total Phenolic Content and Coloration of ‘Hass’ Avocado Subjected to UV-C
939 Radiation. *Nat Prod J* [Internet]. 2012;2:164–170. doi:
940 10.2174/2210315511202030164.
- 941 91. Nowosad K, Sujka M, Pankiewicz U, Kowalski R. The application of PEF
942 technology in food processing and human nutrition. *J. Food Sci. Technol.*
943 Springer; 2021. p. 397–411.
- 944 92. Punthi F, Yudhistira B, Gavahian M, Chang CK, Cheng KC, Hou CY, Hsieh
945 CW. Pulsed electric field-assisted drying: A review of its underlying
946 mechanisms, applications, and role in fresh produce plant-based food
947 preservation. *Compr Rev Food Sci Food Saf.* 2022;21:5109–5130. doi:
948 10.1111/1541-4337.13052. Cited in: : PMID: 36199192.
- 949 93. Dalvi-Isfahan M, Hamdami N, Le-Bail A, Xanthakis E. The principles of high
950 voltage electric field and its application in food processing: A review. *Food Res.*
951 Int. Elsevier Ltd; 2016. p. 48–62.
- 952 94. Liu X, Sun J, Qi X, Mao X. Effect of low intensity direct-current electric field on
953 anti-browning of apple juice: Enzyme inactivation kinetics and juice properties.
954 *Innov Food Sci Emerg Technol.* 2024;92. doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2024.103592.
- 955 95. Zhang Z, Zhang B, Yang R, Zhao W. Recent Developments in the Preservation
956 of Raw Fresh Food by Pulsed Electric Field. *Food Rev. Int.* Taylor and Francis
957 Ltd.; 2022. p. 247–265.
- 958 96. Faridnia F, Burritt DJ, Bremer PJ, Oey I. Innovative approach to determine the

- 959 effect of pulsed electric fields on the microstructure of whole potato tubers: Use
960 of cell viability, microscopic images and ionic leakage measurements. *Food Res*
961 *Int.* 2015;77:556–564. doi: 10.1016/j.foodres.2015.08.028.
- 962 97. Castorena-García JH, Martínez-Montes FJ, Robles-López MR, Welti-Chanes JS,
963 Hernández-Sánchez H, Robles-De-La-Torre RR. Effect of Electric Fields on the
964 Activity of Polyphenol Oxidases [Internet]. *Rev. Mex. Ing. Química.* 2013.
965 Available from: www.rmiq.org.
- 966 98. Miñano HLA, de Sousa Silva AC, Souto S, Costa EJX. Magnetic fields in food
967 processing perspectives, applications and action models. *Processes.* MDPI AG;
968 2020.
- 969 99. Grigelmo-Miguel N, Soliva-Fortuny R, Barbosa-Cánovas G V., Martín-Belloso
970 O. *Use of Oscillating Magnetic Fields in Food Preservation.* Wiley-Blackwell;
971 2011.
- 972 100. Lv L, Jin Y, Yang N, Zhang L, Cui B, Xu X, Jin Z. Effect of alternating magnetic
973 field on the quality of fresh-cut apples in cold storage. *Int J Food Sci Technol.*
974 2022;57:5429–5438. doi: 10.1111/ijfs.15875.
- 975 101. Kaur M, Kumar M. An Innovation in Magnetic Field Assisted Freezing of
976 Perishable Fruits and Vegetables: A Review. *Food Rev. Int.* Bellwether
977 Publishing, Ltd.; 2020. p. 761–780.
- 978 102. Wang T, Jin Y, Yang N, Xu D, Yang Z, Tan Y, Xu X, Jin Z, Cui B. Effect of
979 magnetic field with different dimensions on quality of avocado puree during
980 frozen storage. *Int J Food Sci Technol* [Internet]. 2022;57:1698–1707. doi:
981 10.1111/ijfs.15538.

- 982 103. Ding Y, Mo W, Deng Z, Kimatu BM, Gao J, Fang D. Storage Quality Variation
983 of Mushrooms (*Flammulina velutipes*) after Cold Plasma Treatment. *Life*.
984 2023;13. doi: 10.3390/life13010070.
- 985 104. Batista JDF, Dantas AM, dos Santos Fonseca JV, Madruga MS, Fernandes FAN,
986 Rodrigues S, da Silva Campelo Borges G. Effects of cold plasma on avocado
987 pulp (*Persea americana* Mill.): Chemical characteristics and bioactive
988 compounds. *J Food Process Preserv* [Internet]. 2021;45. doi: 10.1111/jfpp.15179.
- 989 105. Mayookha VP, Pandiselvam R, Kothakota A, Padma Ishwarya S, Chandra
990 Khanashyam A, Kutlu N, Rifna EJ, Kumar M, Panesar PS, Abd El-Maksoud AA.
991 Ozone and cold plasma: Emerging oxidation technologies for inactivation of
992 enzymes in fruits, vegetables, and fruit juices. *Food Control*. Elsevier Ltd; 2023.
- 993 106. Prithviraj V, Pandiselvam R, Babu AC, Kothakota A, Manikantan MR, Ramesh
994 S V., Beegum PPS, Mathew AC, Hebbar KB. Emerging non-thermal processing
995 techniques for preservation of tender coconut water. *LWT*. 2021;149. doi:
996 10.1016/j.lwt.2021.111850.
- 997 107. O'Donnell CP. Ozone in food processing. O'Donnell C, Tiwari BK, Cullen PJ,
998 Rice RG, editors. Blackwell Publishing Ltd; 2012.
- 999 108. FDA F and DA. Regulation FDA Ozone. 2023;
- 1000 109. Panigrahi C, Mishra HN, De S. Effect of ozonation parameters on nutritional and
1001 microbiological quality of sugarcane juice. *J Food Process Eng*. 2020;43. doi:
1002 10.1111/jfpe.13542.
- 1003 110. Liu J, Chang M chang, Meng J long, Liu J yu, Cheng YF, Feng C ping. Effect of
1004 ozone treatment on the quality and enzyme activity of *Lentinus edodes* during

- 1005 cold storage. *J Food Process Preserv.* 2020;44. doi: 10.1111/jfpp.14557.
- 1006 111. Xu D, Shi M, Jia B, Yan Z, Gao L, Guan W, Wang Q, Zuo J. Effect of ozone on
1007 the activity of antioxidant and chlorophyll-degrading enzymes during postharvest
1008 storage of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.). *J Food Process Preserv.* 2019;43.
1009 doi: 10.1111/jfpp.14020.
- 1010 112. Abd El-Moniem EAA, Yousef ARM, Abdel-Razek AG, Badr AN, Mahmoud
1011 TSM. Effects of Postharvest Gaseous Ozone Treatment on Quality Attributes and
1012 Extending Storage Life of Fresh Cut ‘Hass’ Avocado Fruits.’ *Egypt J Chem*
1013 [Internet]. 2022;65:27–37. doi: 10.21608/EJCHEM.2022.133146.5917.
- 1014 113. Mahajan P V., Lee DS. Modified atmosphere and moisture condensation in
1015 packaged fresh produce: Scientific efforts and commercial success. *Postharvest*
1016 *Biol. Technol.* Elsevier B.V.; 2023.
- 1017 114. Qu P, Zhang M, Fan K, Guo Z. Microporous modified atmosphere packaging to
1018 extend shelf life of fresh foods: A review. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* Taylor and
1019 Francis Ltd.; 2022. p. 51–65.
- 1020 115. Wang L, Sun D-W. Rapid cooling of porous and moisture foods by using vacuum
1021 cooling technology. *Trends Food Sci Technol* [Internet]. 2001 [cited 2024 Apr
1022 18];12:174–184. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244\(01\)00077-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244(01)00077-2).
- 1023 116. Bozkurt S, Görgüç A, Gençdağ E, Elmas F, Koç M, Yılmaz FM. Principles and
1024 recent applications of vacuum technology in the processing of dough-based
1025 cereal products: A comprehensive review. *Food Chem.* Elsevier Ltd; 2023.
- 1026 117. Prabath Pathirana UA, Sekozawa Y, Sugaya S, Gemma H. Changes in lipid
1027 oxidation stability and antioxidant properties of avocado in response to 1-MCP

1028 and low oxygen treatment under low-temperature storage. *Int Food Res J*
1029 [Internet]. 2013;20:1065–1075.

1030 118. Gerdes DL, Parrino-Lowe V. Modified atmosphere packaging (map) of fuerte
1031 avocado halves. *LWT - Food Sci Technol* [Internet]. 1995;28:12–16. doi:
1032 10.1016/S0023-6438(95)80005-0.

1033 119. Fuentealba C, Vidal J, Zulueta C, Ponce E, Uarrota V, Defilippi BG, Pedreschi
1034 R. Controlled Atmosphere Storage Alleviates Hass Avocado Black Spot
1035 Disorder. *Horticulturae* [Internet]. 2022;8. doi: 10.3390/horticulturae8050369.

1036

1037 **Figure captions:**

1038 Figure 1: Avocado pulp enzymatic browning

1039 Figure 2. Output search results of Avocado

1040 Figure 3. Schematic representation of HHP